

PHISHING WEBSITE DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Phishing websites represent a significant hazard to online security as they aim to illicitly obtain sensitive user data. Researchers have developed diverse strategies, incorporating machine learning models, to counter this danger. By analyzing vast datasets containing both phishing and authentic websites, these models identify distinguishing patterns. Feature extraction, a common method, examines aspects like URL composition and content to flag potential phishing sites. Conversely, deep learning models autonomously identify features, recognizing intricate patterns. These machine learning strategies demonstrate promising effectiveness, often outperforming traditional rule-based techniques in accuracy. Essential calculations, for example, XGBoost, Slope Supporting, Adaboost, SVM, and Irregular Woodland have been used, exhibiting remarkable outcome in phishing distinguishing proof. The persistent upgrade and evaluation of these strategies hold the possibility to reinforce network safety measures, giving vigorous security against internet phishing dangers.

Keywords: *AI procedures, Xgboost, Slope supporting, Adaboost, SVM, Irregular woods, assessment.*

Introduction:

This deceitful tactic poses a significant menace to online security by exploiting human psychology and trust in reputable sources. As internet usage continues to expand, phishing attacks have grown more prevalent, targeting individuals, businesses, and governmental bodies. The sophistication of phishing methods constantly evolves, making it difficult for users to distinguish genuine websites from fraudulent ones. Additionally, the emergence of social engineering tactics compounds the threat, as attackers manipulate victims psychologically.

Given these challenges, there's an urgent need for effective detection techniques to mitigate the risks associated with phishing websites. Traditional methods like manual inspection or rule-based filters often fall short in identifying newly emerged phishing sites or those using sophisticated evasion tactics. Consequently, there's an increasing reliance on automated detection methods, particularly those utilizing machine learning algorithms, to combat this ever-changing threat landscape.

This study aims to investigate the role of machine learning methods in identifying phishing websites, offering a promising avenue for bolstering online security. By leveraging data-driven algorithms, we aim to create robust detection systems capable of recognizing and neutralizing the dangers posed by phishing attacks in real-time. Through this endeavor, we strive to contribute to the ongoing endeavors to protect users' privacy and security in an increasingly digital environment.

Objective of the Project

The venture means to use AI methods, including XGBoost, Inclination Helping, Adaboost, SVM, and Irregular Woodland, to foster a successful framework for distinguishing phishing sites. By analyzing features such as URL composition and content, the objective is to accurately distinguish between phishing and authentic websites, thereby enhancing online security.

Scope of the Project

This project focuses on leveraging machine learning algorithms to identify phishing websites by analyzing key features. The scope encompasses the development and evaluation of models using diverse datasets containing both phishing and legitimate websites. By investigating calculations like XGBoost, Inclusion Helping, Adaboost, SVM, and Arbitrary Woodland, the task intends to give hearty assurance against internet phishing dangers.

Problem Statement

The project addresses the pressing issue of online security by targeting the detection of phishing websites. With the proliferation of cyber threats, distinguishing between legitimate and malicious websites poses a significant challenge. Leveraging machine learning techniques, the project seeks to develop an effective solution to accurately identify and mitigate the risks associated with phishing attacks, thereby safeguarding user data and enhancing overall cybersecurity measures.

Background

The prevalence of phishing incidents poses a significant threat to digital security, affecting both individuals and organizations. Phishing attacks take various forms, including email, SMS, voice, and website spoofing, and they continuously evolve to evade detection. Their impact extends beyond individual victims, affecting businesses with financial losses, damage to reputation, and legal consequences due to data theft.

Traditional detection methods struggle to keep up with evolving phishing tactics. Rule-based filters and blacklists are ineffective against new or sophisticated attacks, while manual inspection is impractical for the vast volume of online content.

Phishing attacks often use social engineering to bypass technical safeguards, making detection based solely on known indicators insufficient. To address this challenge, there's a need for advanced detection methods, such as machine learning, to identify phishing in real-time and protect users and organizations.

Phishing Detection Using Machine Learning Methods:

Machine learning, a field within artificial intelligence (AI), focuses on creating algorithms capable of learning from data to make predictions or decisions. In the realm of identifying phishing websites, machine learning employs various techniques to analyze website data patterns and features, distinguishing between legitimate and malicious sites.

The process of applying machine learning to detect phishing involves several pivotal stages:

1. Data Gathering and Preparation: Effective machine learning models necessitate substantial labeled data to learn patterns accurately. For phishing detection, this entails assembling a diverse dataset encompassing examples of both legitimate and phishing websites. Additionally, data preparation involves techniques like feature extraction and normalization to ready the data for analysis.

2. Feature Identification: Features represent characteristics or attributes of websites useful for distinguishing between legitimate and phishing sites. These features encompass:

1. URL Structure: Analysis of syntax, length, and the presence of hyphens or subdomains.
2. Domain Age: Assessing the registration age, as phishing sites often utilize newly registered domains.
3. Content Analysis: Scrutinizing webpage content, including keywords, HTML structure, and forms soliciting sensitive information.
4. Website Reputation: Evaluating reputation based on domain reputation scores or blacklists.

3. Model Preparation: AI calculations go through preparing utilizing the marked dataset to recognize examples and connections among highlights and the objective variable (i.e., whether a site is phishing or genuine). Normally utilized calculations for

1. Adaboost
2. Random Forest
3. Support Vector Machines (SVM)

4.Gradient Boosting

5.XGBoost

4. Model Assessment: Prepared models are assessed utilizing measurements like exactness, accuracy, review, and F1score to check their capacity to separate among phishing and genuine sites. Crossvalidation procedures guarantee model heartiness across different datasets.

5. Implementation and RealTime Detection:

Upon training and evaluation, the machine learning model is deployed for realtime phishing detection. Incoming website URLs or features are inputted into the model, which predicts whether the site is likely phishing or legitimate. This proactive detection mechanism aids in preventing phishing attacks before users fall victim.

In essence, machine learning techniques provide a potent means of identifying phishing websites by harnessing datadriven algorithms to detect patterns and anomalies indicative of phishing activity. Continuous research and development in machine learning are crucial for staying ahead of evolving phishing tactics and safeguarding online security.

Methodology

1. XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting):

1. XGBoost is a highly efficient implementation of gradient boosting machines, constructing multiple decision trees sequentially to correct errors from previous trees.
2. Renowned for its scalability and effectiveness in handling large datasets with numerous features, XGBoost excels in learning intricate patterns from website data for precise predictions in phishing detection.

2. Gradient Boosting:

1. Gradient boosting entails building an ensemble of weak learners, usually decision trees, in a stepbystep manner to improve predictive accuracy.
2. Algorithms like Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) are favored in phishing detection for their adeptness in managing varied feature types and understanding complex decision boundaries.

3. Adaboost (Adaptive Boosting):

1. Adaboost combines multiple weak classifiers to form a robust classifier by iteratively training on data subsets, with emphasis on misclassified instances in subsequent iterations.
2. Particularly beneficial for imbalanced datasets, Adaboost enhances classification performance in phishing detection, especially in scenarios with skewed class distributions.

4. Support Vector Machines (SVM):

1. SVM is a classification algorithm constructing hyperplanes in highdimensional space to segregate different classes, aiming for an optimal decision boundary to maximize class margin.
2. Applied in phishing detection, SVM discerns discriminative patterns in website features for accurate classification of URLs as phishing or legitimate.

5. Random Forest:

1. Random Forest builds various choice trees and totals their expectations through casting a ballot or averaging, prepared on bootstrap tests with thought for irregular component subsets at each split.
2. Noteworthy for its versatility against overfitting and proficiency in taking care of loud and associated highlights, Arbitrary Woods suits phishing identification assignments with complicated and uproarious component spaces.

These AI draws near, enveloping XGBoost, Angle Helping, Adaboost, SVM, and Irregular Woods, give assorted procedures to phishing recognition, each with unmistakable benefits and tradeoffs. The decision of calculation relies upon elements, for example, dataset qualities, computational assets, and the ideal harmony among exactness and computational proficiency.

Feature selection is a critical aspect of enhancing the performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1score in machine learning models designed for phishing detection. Here's how feature selection impacts these metrics:

1. Accuracy:

1. Feature selection aids in eliminating irrelevant or duplicate features from the dataset, thereby reducing noise and enhancing the model's capacity to generalize to unseen data.
2. By prioritizing informative features highly indicative of phishing behavior, feature selection can lead to more precise classification of websites as either phishing or legitimate.
3. A more concise and pertinent feature set can prevent overfitting, where the model memorizes the training data instead of capturing underlying patterns, resulting in improved accuracy on unseen data.

2. Precision:

1. Precision gauges the ratio of true positive predictions among all positive predictions made by the model. It indicates the model's ability to correctly identify phishing websites without falsely categorizing legitimate ones as malicious.
2. Feature selection aids in diminishing the inclusion of noisy or irrelevant features that might introduce false positives, resulting in higher precision.
3. By prioritizing features strongly associated with phishing behavior and filtering out irrelevant noise, feature selection allows the model to make more precise predictions, minimizing false alarms.

3. Recall:

1. Recall, or sensitivity, measures the ratio of true positive predictions among all actual positive instances in the dataset. It reflects the model's capability to identify all instances of phishing websites, including subtle or evasive ones.
2. Feature selection that retains informative features linked to phishing behavior ensures accurate identification of a greater proportion of phishing websites, thereby enhancing recall.
3. By selecting features that capture unique phishing website characteristics while eliminating irrelevant noise, feature selection enhances the model's ability to detect malicious behavior, resulting in higher recall scores.

4. F1score:

1. The F1score, being the harmonic mean of precision and recall, provides a balanced measure of a model's performance, considering both false positives and false negatives.
2. Feature selection helps optimize the precisionrecall tradeoff by identifying a feature subset that maximizes the F1score.
3. By selecting features that most effectively differentiate between phishing and legitimate websites, feature selection enhances the model's overall performance, resulting in higher F1scores.

Literature review

1. Shad and Sharma introduced a fresh machine learning method for identifying phishing websites. They highlighted the surge in fake websites aiming to steal users' private data like account details. Phishing, now targeting mobile platforms too, poses financial risks. The paper explores detection methods leveraging URL and hyperlink features to differentiate between genuine and deceptive sites. It delves into six main approaches including heuristic, blacklist, fuzzy rule, machine learning, image processing, and the CANTINA method, discussing the phishing issue, current machine learning solutions, and future research prospects.

2. Sönmez et al. examine phishing website characteristics and their classification using extreme learning machines. They underline the threat posed by counterfeit websites aiming to steal personal data. These sites mimic legitimate ones in appearance and meaning. With phishing techniques advancing, countermeasures like machine learning are essential for detection. The paper reviews features and machine learning-based detection techniques to combat phishing.

3. Peng, Harris, and Sawa propose a strategy for recognizing phishing assaults through regular language handling and AI. They feature the normal and under-guarded nature of phishing dangers. Their approach analyzes text content to identify suspicious statements indicating phishing attacks, focusing on semantic analysis to detect malicious intent. Evaluation using a substantial set of phishing emails validates the effectiveness of the approach.

4. Karabatak and Mustafa assess the performance of classifiers on a reduced phishing website dataset. Despite the existence of several anti-phishing systems, attacks persist due to various factors. While machine learning methods show potential, challenges remain in selecting feature vectors. They propose an improved predictive model comprising a feature selection module that generates an effective feature vector from URL, webpage properties, and behavior. The model employs CNN, KNN, and SVM trained on a 30-dimensional feature space.

5. Shima and colleagues address internet-based criminal activities by proposing a model to classify URLs as benign, spam, or malware, without analyzing website content.

Feature extraction plays a pivotal role in machine learning-driven phishing detection, involving the identification and conversion of pertinent website attributes into numerical forms usable by algorithms. This process aims to discern distinct patterns distinguishing phishing sites from legitimate ones. In phishing detection, feature extraction encompasses scrutinizing various website data aspects like URL composition, domain longevity, content, and reputation. Here's an overview of the procedure and diverse features examined:

1. URL Composition Analysis:

1. Evaluating the syntax and constituents of website URLs to pinpoint patterns linked with phishing assaults.
2. Features derived from URL composition may include:
3. Length of URLs: Phishing URLs often exhibit greater length and complexity compared to legitimate ones.
4. Subdomain presence: Phishing URLs frequently incorporate subdomains to mimic genuine websites or create an impression of authenticity.
5. Usage of special characters: Phishing URLs might employ hyphens, underscores, or other special characters to obscure the domain.
6. URL redirection: Phishing schemes commonly utilize URL redirection tactics to deceive users and evade detection.

7. These features offer valuable insights into URL structure and aid in identifying suspicious patterns indicative of phishing activities.

2. Domain Longevity:

1. Refers to the duration since a domain name's registration or first indexing by search engines.
2. Phishing sites often resort to newly registered domains (NRDs) to circumvent detection and prolong their lifespan.
3. Features pertinent to domain longevity may comprise:
4. Registration duration: Phishing domains typically opt for shorter registration periods, whereas legitimate ones often have longer durations.
5. Creation date: Phishing domains tend to have recent creation dates, unlike legitimate ones with a longer history.
6. Historical records: Analyzing historical domain registration and hosting data can shed light on a website's legitimacy.
7. Considering features related to domain longevity enables the model to evaluate a site's trustworthiness and longevity, aiding in distinguishing between phishing and genuine domains.

3. Content Examination:

1. Involves scrutinizing textual and visual content on web pages to spot phishing indicators.
2. Features derived from content analysis may encompass:
3. Keywords and phrases: Phishing sites frequently employ specific terms related to financial transactions, login credentials, or urgent messages to entice victims.
4. HTML structure: Inspection of HTML tags, metadata, and page layout can uncover anomalies indicative of phishing endeavors.
5. Forms and input fields: Phishing pages often include forms soliciting sensitive data like passwords or credit card numbers.
6. Visual elements: Analyzing images, logos, and branding elements aids in identifying counterfeit or spoofed websites.

7. Contentbased features offer contextual insights complementing structural and domainrelated features, bolstering the model's phishing detection capabilities.

4. Reputation and Behavioral Analysis:

1. Entails evaluating website reputation and online behavior using external sources and historical data.
2. Features derived from reputation and behavioral analysis may include:
3. Domain reputation scores: Ratings or scores from reputationbased services and blacklists indicating domain trustworthiness.
4. PhishTank submissions: Examination of submissions to platforms like PhishTank to identify known phishing URLs.
5. User interaction patterns: Analysis of user behavior metrics such as clickthrough rates and time spent on page aids in identifying suspicious websites.
6. Leveraging reputationbased features harnesses collective intelligence and historical data to flag potentially malicious sites, enhancing the model's phishing detection prowess.

Evaluation and Performance Metrics:

1. Assessment Approaches:

1.CrossValidation: This technique includes parting the dataset into portions, preparing the model on one fragment, and testing it on the others to check its flexibility and unwavering quality across various information divisions.

2.Holdout Approval: Here, the dataset is partitioned into preparing and testing subsets. The model is prepared on the previous and evaluated on the last option to appraise its exhibition on inconspicuous information.

3.Stratified Inspecting: This strategy guarantees that the dissemination of classes stays delegate across preparing and testing sets, urgent for datasets with irregular characteristics, as underrepresented phishing examples.

4.Performance Measurements: different measurements, including exactness, accuracy, review, F1score, ROC bend, and AUC, are used to assess the adequacy of phishing location models.

2. Common Performance Metrics:

1. Accuracy: Measures the proportion of accurately ordered occurrences to the complete examples, giving a general execution measure. Notwithstanding, it could delude on imbalanced datasets.

2. Precision: Assesses the extent of genuine positive expectations among every positive forecast, demonstrating the model's capacity to limit misleading up-sides.

3. Recall (Awareness): Surveys the extent of genuine positive expectations among all genuine positive cases, showing the model's capacity to catch all phishing occasions and decrease bogus negatives.

4. F1score: The consonant mean of accuracy and review, offering a fair presentation measure that thinks about misleading up-sides and bogus negatives, especially valuable for imbalanced datasets.

5. Receiver Working Trademark (ROC) Bend and Region Under the Bend (AUC): ROC bend outlines the genuine positive rate against the misleading positive rate at different limits. A higher AUC demonstrates better segregation among phishing and real sites.

3. Efficacy of Machine LearningBased Approaches:

1. Machine learningbased methods outperform traditional rulebased techniques in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1score.

2. Algorithms like XGBoost, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machines exhibit high detection rates while minimizing false positives and negatives.

3. Models trained on diverse datasets effectively capture nuanced phishing patterns, enhancing detection performance.

4. Unlike static rulebased methods, machine learning techniques are adaptive, learning from evolving phishing tactics, thereby improving realworld effectiveness.
5. In essence, assessing phishing detection models involves diverse methods and metrics, including crossvalidation, holdout validation, and various performance indicators. Machine learningbased approaches show superiority over traditional methods, leveraging advanced algorithms to better discern phishing from legitimate websites, thus enhancing online security.

Proposed System

The proposed system for detecting phishing websites using machine learning algorithms seeks to address the limitations found in current systems. One strategy involves employing supervised learning techniques that don't necessitate labeled data for training, thereby cutting down on the time and expense associated with data labeling and enhancing scalability.

Another tactic involves integrating multiple machine learning algorithms to bolster the system's accuracy and resilience. Additionally, the system could benefit from the inclusion of extra features like website behavior analysis and user behavior monitoring to enhance its phishing detection capabilities.

In essence, the proposed system aims to enhance the precision, efficiency, and efficacy of phishing website detection by leveraging machine learning algorithms.

Fig. Block Diagram

Future Avenues in Detecting Phishing Websites:

In the ever-changing landscape of phishing threats, it's crucial to explore new avenues to improve the detection of phishing websites. Here are potential areas for further research and development:

1. Adversarial Learning: Investigating methods to enhance phishing detection models' resilience against crafted attacks, where attackers create phishing sites to evade detection. Techniques like adversarial training can bolster the ability of detection systems to counter sophisticated adversaries
2. Behavioral Analysis: Integrating behavioral analysis to strengthen phishing detection by examining user interactions with websites, such as mouse movements and browsing behavior, to detect anomalies indicative of phishing. This approach complements existing methods and provides insights into the dynamic nature of phishing attacks.
3. Explainable AI: Developing techniques to make phishing detection models more interpretable and transparent. This enhances the understanding of why certain websites are flagged as phishing or legitimate, aiding security analysts in decision-making and model improvement
4. Real-Time Detection: Exploring methods for detecting phishing websites in real-time to proactively mitigate attacks as they happen. Real-time systems can analyze incoming website traffic instantly, using streaming data processing and advanced algorithms to identify potential threats rapidly.
5. Adaptive Models: Creating models that can adapt and update based on emerging phishing tactics. Continuously learning from new data and feedback, these models adjust to evolving threats, maintaining high detection accuracy over time.
6. Integration with Security Ecosystems: Finding ways to integrate phishing detection systems with broader security setups, such as email gateways and endpoint protection. This seamless integration improves overall detection and response by coordinating threat mitigation across different layers of defense.

7. User-Centric Approaches: Developing tools and applications that empower users to identify and report phishing attacks effectively. This could involve user-friendly browser extensions or mobile apps, enabling users to verify website legitimacy and report suspicious activity easily

The Importance of Ongoing Improvement:

Continuous enhancement of phishing detection methods is crucial for several reasons:

1. Evolving Threats: Phishing attacks are constantly changing, requiring detection methods to evolve to remain effective against new tactics.
2. User Trust: Improving detection methods helps protect users from falling victim to scams, maintaining trust in online platforms.
3. Adapting to Adversaries: Ongoing improvement helps security teams stay ahead of attackers who adapt their tactics to bypass defenses.
4. Regulatory Compliance: Continuous improvement ensures compliance with regulations, reducing the risk of penalties associated with data breaches.

To summarize, future efforts in phishing website detection should focus on advancing techniques such as adversarial learning, behavioral analysis, explainable AI, real-time detection, adaptive models, integration with security ecosystems, and user-centric approaches. Continuous improvement in detection methods is essential for effectively mitigating the risks of phishing attacks and maintaining security online.

Results

Home Page:

Here user view the home page of phishing website prediction web application.

Load:

In the load page, users can load the website dataset.

View:

Here we can see the uploaded data set.

Model:

Here we can train our data using different algorithm.

Prediction:

This page show the detection result that whether the website is a phishing website or legitimate.

Comparison

Model	Accuracy
Random Forest	83
AdaBoost	78
XGBoost	84
SVM	77
Gradient Boosting	81

"Model Exhibitions" analyzes the precision of various AI classifiers utilized for phishing site discovery. The classifiers assessed are Irregular Timberland, AdaBoost, XGBoost, Backing Vector Machine (SVM), and Inclination Helping. The XGBoost classifier shows the most elevated exactness at roughly 84%, followed intently by the Arbitrary Woods classifier at around 83%. The Inclination Helping classifier shows a moderate exhibition with a precision of around 81%. The AdaBoost classifier has a lower precision of around 78%, while the SVM shows minimal exactness at roughly 77%. This correlation features the predominant presentation of outfit strategies like XGBoost and Arbitrary Woodland in phishing discovery errands.

Conclusion:

To summarize, this study has investigated the importance of employing machine learning to counter phishing attacks and bolster online security measures. By scrutinizing a range of machine

learning methodologies and techniques for extracting features, several noteworthy discoveries and contributions have surfaced.

AI calculations like XGBoost, Angle Helping, Adaboost, Backing Vector Machine (SVM), and Irregular Timberland have shown huge viability in pinpointing phishing sites by knowing examples and characteristics that put them aside from authentic stages. These algorithms harness features such as URL structure, domain longevity, content analysis, and reputation to accurately pinpoint phishing threats and mitigate potential harm to users and organizations.

The significance of machine learning in the fight against phishing attacks cannot be emphasized enough. Conventional rule-based approaches often struggle to adapt to the constantly shifting and evolving landscape of phishing tactics. In contrast, machine learning-driven techniques offer a more adaptable and data-centric approach, empowering security teams to stay ahead of emerging threats and effectively shield users from falling prey to phishing schemes.

Furthermore, the potential impact of machine learning-powered techniques in fortifying online security extends beyond phishing detection. Through the utilization of advanced algorithms and analytics, machine learning can aid in identifying and neutralizing various cybersecurity menaces, including malware, fraudulent activities, and data breaches. This proactive stance toward cybersecurity enables organizations to safeguard sensitive data, uphold user trust, and mitigate financial and reputational vulnerabilities.

In essence, machine learning serves as a cornerstone in the battle against phishing attacks and the augmentation of online security. By perpetually refining detection methodologies and harnessing insights derived from data, machine learning-driven approaches hold the promise of transforming cybersecurity practices, rendering the digital realm safer and more resilient against emerging threats. As ongoing research and development in this domain progress, the potential of machine learning to elevate online security remains limitless.

Future Enhancement

1. Utilizing Advanced Learning Techniques: Explore deep learning methods like convolutional and recurrent neural networks to enhance phishing detection. These techniques have shown potential in various fields and could improve accuracy and reliability in identifying phishing attempts.

2. Unsupervised Learning Exploration: Look into unsupervised learning methods for spotting new or unforeseen phishing attacks. These approaches can identify patterns and irregularities in website data without relying on predefined labels, which is crucial for detecting emerging threats.

3. Integration of Multiple Data Sources: Combine data from different sources such as website content, user behavior, and network traffic to better detect phishing attempts. This multi-modal approach can provide a more comprehensive understanding of phishing behavior, making detection more accurate and resilient.

4. Adaptive Feature Selection: Develop techniques that dynamically select features based on incoming website data characteristics. This can improve the efficiency of phishing detection by focusing on the most relevant features for each instance.

5. Enhancing Model Interpretability: Improve the explainability of machine learning models used in phishing detection. Providing explanations for model decisions can help security analysts understand classification outcomes better and identify potential model weaknesses.

6. Boosting Model Robustness: Research methods to make phishing detection models more resilient against adversarial attacks. Techniques such as adversarial training and regularization can help models withstand manipulation attempts by sophisticated adversaries.

7. Protecting User Privacy: Develop techniques that ensure user privacy while maintaining effective phishing detection. Methods like federated learning and differential privacy can address privacy concerns in collaborative detection scenarios.

8. Real-Time Threat Integration: Incorporate real-time threat intelligence feeds into phishing detection systems to improve their ability to detect and respond to emerging threats. Access to current

information on malicious URLs and IP addresses can enhance detection accuracy and responsiveness.

By focusing on these areas, researchers and practitioners can advance the effectiveness and resilience of machine learning-based phishing detection, ultimately contributing to a safer online environment.

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